

SYNTHESIS OF CYANINE DYES BY THE CONDENSATION OF
p-DIETHYLAMINOBENZALDEHYDE WITH APPROPRIATE
HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART III

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The effect on sensitisation of substitution and multiplication of groups in the thiazole and benzothiazole nuclei of *p*-diethylaminostyrylthiazole and *p*-diethylaminostyrylbenzothiazole methiodides has been studied. For this purpose four new dyes have been synthesised by condensing the methiodides of 2:5-dimethylthiazole, 2:4:5-trimethylthiazole, 2:6-dimethylbenzothiazole and 2:4:6-trimethylbenzothiazole with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde. The optical, chemical, dyeing and photographic properties of these compounds have been studied. A few "intermediates" have been described.

It has been observed that the extrasensitisation, conferred on gelatino-silver bromide photographic plates by a cyanine dye, is considerably influenced by the effect of different substituent groups in different positions of the dye molecule. Thus, Mills and Pope (*Phot. J.*, 1920, 44, 183) have observed that the introduction of a methyl group in 6-position in both 1:1'-dimethyl and 1:1'-diethylisocyanine iodides, broadens the extrasensitisation bands and heightens their intensity, while the introduction of the methyl group in the 2'-position has the opposite effect.

The absorption is also profoundly affected by substituents in different positions of a dye molecule. Thus, groups in 6- and 6'-positions of ethyl red are more potent in their effect than methyl and cause a greater shift, and the dimethylamino groups are the most powerful of all (*cf.* Mees, "The Theory of Photographic Process", MacMillan Company, New York, 1944, p. 1022). The amino group by itself markedly augments the sensitising power of the 1:1'-dimethylisocyanine, when introduced into the 5, 6 or 6'-position though the spectrographs indicate surprisingly little difference between the effects produced by the amino-substitution in the three alternate positions. The introduction of the acetamino group in the above dye, however, has a depressing effect on the sensitising power, an effect which is influenced by the position of the substituent (Mills and Pope, *loc. cit.*).

So far no systematic investigation has been carried out on the effect of different substituent groups in the quaternised nuclei of *p*-dialkylaminostyryl type of cyanine dyes, though it is known that an increase in the molecular weight of the dye has often led to enhanced sensitisation, instances of the opposite effect being not uncommon. It was thus of interest to study the effect of substitution of different groups on sensitisation, in the quaternised thiazole and benzothiazole nuclei of 2-*p*-diethylaminostyrylthiazole methiodide (I) and 2-*p*-diethylaminostyryl-benzothiazole methiodide (II).

Fig 1

Unbathed

It will be seen that two positions, 4 and 5, are available for substitution in (I), while four positions, 4,5,6 and 7, are available in (II). Four dyes have been prepared by condensing the methiodides of 2:5-dimethylthiazole, 2:4:5-trimethylthiazole, 2:6-dimethylbenzothiazole and 2:4:6-trimethylbenzothiazole with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde in absolute alcohol solution using small quantities of piperidine as catalyst. The dye (I) with a 4-methyl substitution has been described in a previous communication (Doja and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 217).

The first two methiodides containing simple thiazole systems condense less readily than the methiodides containing condensed thiazole systems (cf. Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) as the dyes in the latter case crystallise out of the alcoholic solution quite easily and are obtained in good yield after about 6 hours of refluxing, while the dyes in the former case could not be crystallised out of the alcoholic solution even after refluxing for 72 hours and had to be precipitated out of the alcoholic solution with ether.

Some of the properties of these dyes are summarised in Table I.

The dyes are feebly soluble in cold, but more so in boiling water, and are freely soluble in alcohols and acetic acid but are insoluble in ether.

Dilute alcoholic solutions of the substituted simple thiazole dyes (Q) and (R) are orange-yellow, while those of the substituted condensed thiazoles (S) and (T) are magenta coloured. The relative intensities of dilute solutions (1:10,000) in rectified spirit, as determined by Dubosq colorimeter, are given in Table I. It will be noticed that the colour of (S) is more intense than that of (T), though the latter has an additional methyl group attached to the 4-position.

The colour of the dye solutions is reversibly discharged by the addition of mineral acids, probably due to the destruction of the conjugated systems (cf. Brooker, Sprague, Smyth and Lewis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1116) as indicated in a previous communication (Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*). The relative resistances to decolorisation by *N*/100-HCl are given in Table I. The weaker resistance of (T) than that of (S) is perhaps due to the same effect as renders the colour of the former weaker than that of the latter.

The colour produced on cotton, wool and silk by the dyes (Q) and (R) is orange-yellow, while the dyes (S) and (T) colour them mauve. The shades, however, are not fast to washing and are discharged slowly when exposed to sunlight.

TABLE I

Com- pound.	Colour, shape & form.	Colour in cold conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	M.p.	Reflex.	Pleo-chroism		Relative resistance to decolorisa- tion.	Relative intensity of colour in soln.	Extra-sensitation		Remarks.
					Colour of light in one position of polariser.	Colour of light 1 to titan.			Range in Å	Range in Å	
Q	Mauve, very thin, small needles	Very faint pink	227°	Skyblue (weak)	Weak rose	Deep red	1.53	1	5100- 5900	5600	
R	Deep magenta, stout needles	Faint yello- wish brown	217- 18°	Greenish blue (strong)	Orange	Nearly opaque	1	1.08	5000- 5300	Indistinct	Well formed crystals
S	Golden green, microscopic needles	Brownish yellow	220°	Bottle green (very strong)	Light green	Dirty green	6.74	1	Nil	Nil	Extremely beautiful crystals
T	Dark red needle clusters	Brownish yellow	215°	Yellow	Dark red	Orange-red	6.3	0.98	Nil	Nil	Some faces look like glass under polari- sed light

Q—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-5-methylthiazole methiodide.
 R—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-4:6-dimethylthiazole methiodide.
 S—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-6-methylbenzothiazole methiodide.
 T—2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-4:6-dimethylbenzothiazole methiodide.

TABLE II

Wallace colour filters.										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Q	Light	Deep brown red	Brownish yellow	Orange yellow	Yellowish brown	Lemon- yellow	Light green- ish brown	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Yellowish brown
R	Do	Light absorbed	Weak yellow	Orange yellow	Lemon- yellow	Deep yellow	Greenish brown	Do	Do	Yellowish brown
S	Do	Do	Brown yellow	Brown	Weak yellow	Weak yellow	Light absorbed	Do	Do	Orange yellow
T	Do	Do	Do	Brown deep	Yellowish brown	Light yellow	Do	Do	Do	Yellow

These dyes also show the peculiar phenomenon that their acetic acid solutions deepen in colour on warming and their original colours are regained on cooling, the effect being more pronounced in aqueous acetic acid solutions (cf. Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*).

Photographs of the absorption and sensitisation spectra of the dyes, as determined by a Wedge spectrograph, are shown in Fig.1. None of the dyes is a good sensitiser. The introduction of a methyl group in the 5-position of 2-*p*-diethylaminostyrylthiazole methiodide depresses the sensitisation as compared to the 4-methyl-substituted dye. (cf. Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*). The 4:5-dimethyl-substituted dye shows a still poorer sensitisation.

The 6-methyl and 4:6-dimethyl-substituted 2-*p*-diethylaminostyrylbenzothiazole methiodides show a complete depression in sensitisation as compared to the unsubstituted dye (cf. Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*), which is remarkably a good sensitiser sensitising up to 6350Å.

The fluorescence of these dyes is given in Table II. The colours noted are those of the fluorescent beam at right angles to the incident beam.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:5-Dimethylthiazole methiodide.—2:5-Dimethylthiazole, prepared from α -chloropropion-aldehyde and thioacetamide (*Annalen*, 1890, **259**, 240), was heated with methyl iodide (1:1.5) in a sealed tube for 24 hours. The salt crystallised from absolute alcohol in colorless, flat needles, m.p. 148°, yield 76%. (Found : I, 49.73. $C_6H_{10}NIS$ requires I, 49.8 per cent).

2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-5-methylthiazole methiodide.—2:5-Dimethylthiazole methiodide (0.382 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.265 g.), absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) and piperidine (2 drops) were refluxed for 8 hours. The dye was precipitated out of the solution by adding ether and was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in needles with a weak skyblue reflex, yield 32%. (Found : N, 6.70 ; I, 30.52. $C_{17}H_{23}N_2IS$ requires N, 6.76 ; I, 30.67 per cent).

2:4:5-Trimethylthiazole methiodide.—2:4:5-Trimethylthiazole, prepared from methyl-chloroethyl ketone and thioacetamide (*Annalen*, 1888, **250**, 258) was heated with methyl iodide (1:1.5) in a sealed tube for 24 hours. The salt was recrystallised from rectified spirit in long needles, m.p. 165-66°, yield 86%. (Found : I, 47.36. $C_7H_{12}NIS$ requires I, 47.21 per cent).

2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-4:5-dimethylthiazole methiodide.—2:4:5-Trimethylthiazole methiodide (0.95 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.63 g.), absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) and piperidine (2 drops) were refluxed for 8 hours. The dye was precipitated out of the solution with ether and was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in needles with strong greenish blue reflex, yield 42%. (Found: N, 6.48 ; I, 29.51. $C_{18}H_{25}N_2IS$ requires N, 6.54; I, 29.67 per cent).

2:6-Dimethylbenzothiazole methiodide.—2:6-Dimethylbenzothiazole, prepared from thio-aceto-*p*-toluidide (Jacobson and Ney, *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 907) and methyl iodide (1:1.5) were heated in a sealed tube for 24 hours. The salt crystallised from water in colorless needles, m.p. 247°, yield 78%. (Found: I, 41.58. $C_{10}H_{12}NIS$ requires I, 41.64 per cent).

2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-6-methylbenzothiazole methiodide.—2:6-Dimethylbenzothiazole methiodide (0.305 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.177 g.), absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) and

piperidine (2 drops) were refluxed for 6 hours. The dye crystallised out next day and was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in needles with a strong bottle-green reflex, yield 32%. (Found: N, 6.00; I, 27.29. $C_{21}H_{26}N_2IS$ requires N, 6.04; I, 27.37 per cent).

2:4:6-Trimethylbenzothiazole methiodide.—2:4:6-Trimethylbenzothiazole, prepared from thioaceto-*m*-xylydide (Jacobson and Ney, *loc. cit.*), and methyl iodide (1:1.5) were heated in a sealed tube for 24 hours. The salt was recrystallised from water in long colorless needles, m.p. 227-28°, yield 78%. (Found: I, 39.65. $C_{11}H_{14}NIS$ requires I, 39.81 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-4:6-dimethylbenzothiazole methiodide.—2:4:6-Trimethylbenzothiazole methiodide (0.16 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.089 g.), absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) and piperidine (2 drops) were refluxed for 2 hours. The dye which crystallised out was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in needles with a yellow reflex, yield 38%. (Found: N, 5.80; I, 26.39. $C_{22}H_{27}N_2IS$ requires N, 5.86; I, 26.57 per cent).

One of us (J.C.B.) gratefully records his thanks to the authorities of the Patna University for the grant of a research scholarship to him during a part of the pendency of the work.

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Received January 21, 1949.